

Analysis of a microwave filter parameters for design optimization via machine learning

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Abstract— Microwave filters are essential for filtering and selecting frequencies. They prevent interference, enhance signal quality, and maximize the efficiency of microwave systems. They are widely employed in wireless communications, satellites, and radar systems. To optimize the design of these filters, techniques like machine learning can be utilized, saving time and resources compared to simulations. Machine learning learns from data to discover optimized solutions more swiftly and efficiently, leading to high-performance filters. In this work, analyses of the parameters of a T-inverted filter were performed to serve as a foundation for a machine learning-based design. The filter used was designed and manufactured for a frequency range of 1 GHz to 3 GHz and its measured and simulated results were compared as a way of validating the structure.

Keywords—cluster, machine learning, microwave filter, optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

The design of microwave structures is commonly performed through theoretical calculations and the use of electromagnetic simulation (EM) software [1], [2]. It focuses on how to obtain the device's physical parameters for a given electrical performance. However, the process of calculation and optimization through simulation takes a long time, increasing with the complexity of the filter, until the necessary parameters are determined, because each time the parameter is adjusted, the software needs to perform an EM simulation. Furthermore, if there is a need to adjust the device in other frequency bands or for another application, the entire calculation and simulation process will have to be done again.

Machine learning, as well as in other areas, have been increasingly applied to solve problems in RF/Microwave design [3]-[5]. They are able to learn, after a training process, relationships between the physical and electrical features of devices. This training can be performed from the physical parameters and the S parameters obtained by EM simulation and/or measurement. After its construction, it is possible to model the devices quickly and accurately, according to the desired objective.

In this role, through data clustering, the variables that exhibited the greatest sensitivity to frequency response were

determined and served as a comprehensive database to feed into an artificial neural network was designed and integrated to automate the physical dimensions of a microwave filter, based on an inverted T, for a frequency range from 1 GHz to 3 GHz.

II. EASE OF USE

A. Filter Design

The filter has a compact structure based on an inverted T. The substrate used is RO3010 from Rogers Corporation®, with thickness $h = 1.27$ mm, relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 10.2$ and loss tangent of 0.0022. The filter is 10 mm wide and 40 mm long. The feedline has 50Ω impedance and 1 mm width, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Design of the proposed microwave filter.

The design of the filter was inspired by the concept proposed in [6]. It comprises a geometry-based inverted parallel t-shaped stopband filter. The filter structure consists of a main transmission line in the form of an inverted T, where the central line of the T is perpendicular to the main transmission line. This arrangement creates a parallel load impedance and is hence referred to as a parallel filter [6]. The parallel T-shaped branch functions as a signal rejection branch for the incoming signal from the main transmission line. Its purpose is to attenuate or reject specific frequencies within the operating range of the filter.

The dimensions of the lines and the structure were carefully chosen to ensure that the operating frequency of the system falls within the range of 1 to 3 GHz.

B. Filter Analysis

The device was constructed using a 3D electromagnetic simulation software, and the simulated S-parameter results were obtained.

This study aimed to analyze the S_{21} response of the filter. By focusing on the S_{21} response, which represents the transmission characteristics of the filter, we gain valuable insights into the performance of the filter in attenuating specific frequency ranges [7].

When designing the filter using software, multiple combinations of dimensions can be employed. In Fig. 2 below, ten variables used in the construction of the filter can be observed. The selection of these variables allows for the fine-tuning of the filter's performance and characteristics according to the desired specifications and requirements.

Fig. 2. The filter in the simulation environment and variables used.

From a 2D perspective, the variables a , b , c , d , e , f , g , h , i , and j correspond to lengths within the filter structure. Specifically, variables a , b , c , d , e , and f vary along the x -axis, while variables g , h , i , and j vary along the y -axis. These variables represent key dimensions within the filter's design, governing its geometrical characteristics and defining the spatial arrangement of its components.

In the simulation, the midpoint of the line cd is defined as $(0,0)$. Parameter “ a ” varies in the opposite direction of the x -axis (negative values), while parameter “ b ” varies in the positive direction of the x -axis (positive values). Variable “ h ” varies in the positive direction of the y -axis, while variable “ i ” varies in the opposite direction. The same idea applies to the other six variables. In the simulations, two values were adopted for each variable, taking into account the physical limitations of the filter.

By manipulating these dimensions, such as length, the filter's frequency response, bandwidth, and other performance parameters can be tailored to meet specific design objectives.

A prototype was designed, manufactured, and subjected to measurements in order to assess the effectiveness of the proposed filter. In Fig. 3, a graph is presented illustrating a comparison between the simulated and measured values of a filter. In this filter, the variables used were: $a = -0.6$; $b = 0.7$; $c = -8$; $d = 7.5$; $e = -11$; $f = 11$; $g = 0.8$; $h = 0.3$; $i = -0.3$ and $j = -0.6$.

Fig. 3. Comparison between the simulated and measured values of a filter.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND NETWORK

Several simulations were conducted, resulting from different combinations of the ten variables employed. This endeavor aimed to discern which variables exhibited higher sensitivity towards the S_{21} response in terms of resonance frequency and bandwidth. Furthermore, these simulations served the dual purpose of functioning as a comprehensive database to feed the proposed network.

A. Clusters and most influential variables

Certain variables have a more direct relationship with the S_{21} response of the filter, meaning that the resonance frequency and bandwidth are more sensitive to some variables than others. Through clustering analysis, four variables of higher influence were identified. These variables significantly affect the S_{21} response, exerting a stronger impact on the filter's resonance frequency.

Clusters aid in identifying similar data groups, which machine learning leverages to learn patterns and make decisions. They explore and preprocess data before model training, reducing dimensionality and improving model efficiency and accuracy. Additionally, clusters can be used as benchmarks to evaluate machine learning model quality.

1) Variable D.

The Fig. 4 shows the grouping of results obtained for the point of maximum attenuation at each frequency. Two values of “ d ” were chosen 9.5 and 7.5.

Fig. 4. Resonances - Parameter D.

It can be observed that when the parameter 'd' is set to 7.5, the frequency response is bounded within the range of 1.6 to 2.3 GHz, whereas 'd' equal to 9.5 results in responses within the interval of 1.6 to 2.6 GHz.

2) Variable F.

The Fig. 5 shows the grouping of results obtained for the point of maximum attenuation at each frequency. Two values of "f" were chosen 11 and 9.

It is evident to observe a robust relation between the parameter and the response. When "f" is set to 11, the frequency response of the filter is confined within the range of 1.6 to 2.2 GHz.

Fig. 5. Resonances - Parameter F.

3) Variable G.

Two values of "g" were chosen 0.6 and 0.8. The cluster plot can be seen in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Resonances - Parameter G.

In this case, a more distinct delimitation among the values of the variable can be observed. This division can be accomplished by a straight line, which may indicate the presence of linear separability in the data. Such linear division can be leveraged by machine learning algorithms that are sensitive to linear separations.

4) Variable J.

Two values of "j" were chosen 0.6 and 0.8. The cluster plot can be seen in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Resonances - Parameter J.

This cluster also proves to be valuable as it allows for a more linear relationship between the parameter 'j' and the attenuation values in dB. When 'j' is equal to -0.8, the magnitude in dB is higher compared to when 'j' is equal to -0.6.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an inverted-T microwave filter was designed, simulated and manufactured for a frequency range from 1GHz to 3 GHz. With the use of clustering techniques, the variables that showed the greatest sensitivity to the frequency response of the device were determined. The simulated results obtained by varying these parameters are used as a basis for the bank to feed a machine learning designed to automate the physical dimensions of a microwave filter.

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